

Research Article

Tree Ring Perimeter Calculation and Convergence Analysis Using Euclidean Distance with Interactive Visualization

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Abstract: This research seeks to explore the convergence analysis of tree ring perimeter measurement using the distance formula as a way of furthering understanding about the age of trees and their condition of the environment for their entire life span. In fact, the measurement of the rings is a vital science that provides the important records of the climate of the past as well as of ecological changes. The traditional way discovering the cross-section of the tree rings by using a circle formula might prove to be inaccurate. To obtain accurate perimeter measurements, the coordinates of each tree ring points are defined and the perimeters are calculated with the help of the Euclidean distance formula. This research aims at determining the effect of various weighing factors on the precision and reliability of perimeter calculation for useful analysis of tree rings. Furthermore, the research aims to present the functionals of assigning the difference number of graph coordinates to find the perimeter in Euclidean space converge as the number of points approaches infinity. The results of this work can be used for furthering dendrochronological research by utilizing this method for the accurate measurement of tree ring perimeters. In addition, this improved estimation of tree age and environmental conditions and helps reconstruct more accurately past environmental conditions. The knowledge from this study has theoretical significance and practical application within different areas of study ranging from ecology, climatology and environmental conservation.

Keywords: cross-section; perimeter; dendrochronological.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dendrochronology is the study of the information found in tree rings, where the width of the wood's annual growth is measured. Researchers use this method to understand past climates, tree growth patterns, and the age of trees. By examining specific features, scientists can also assess the health of trees (Divya & Kaur, 2021). As global environmental changes impact ecosystems worldwide (Martinez del Castillo et al, 2022), establishing a strong link between tree growth and climate is crucial.

Once this relationship is established, tree growth is often viewed as a consistent function of climate variables (Peltier & Ogle, 2020).

Measuring the perimeter of tree rings presents significant challenges due to their irregular and complex shapes. At first glance, it appears that the cross-section of a tree is round, but this is not the case, which can result in significant errors. Traditional methods, frequently dependent on oversimplified mathematical models such as the circumference formula of a circle, often encounter difficulties in accurately representing the complex geometries and natural variations inherent in tree growth. These methods can lead to measurements errors, leading to inaccuracies in the scientific data derived from these measurements.

In this project, a numerical analysis will be conducted. Numerical analysis, also known as computational mathematics, focuses on developing methods for numerically solving mathematically posed problems, typically providing approximate solutions. Understanding the principles of numerical analysis is valuable not only for mathematicians but also for practical computation. A clear grasp of these fundamentals aids in developing solution methods for complex problems encountered in real-world applications (Linz, ,2019).

Trace-It is developed to help mitigate this problem by using the Euclidean distance formula. This project provides significant benefits by improving the efficiency of dendrochronologists in the process of counting tree rings. Its user-friendly methodology leads to a significant reduction in time, energy, and resources. The algorithm's accuracy is guaranteed, as it has been tested by extensive convergence analysis.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Method

In the data preparation process, a picture of the tree's cross-section is placed on graph paper, and its outline is carefully traced to capture its shape accurately. A piece of string is then used to follow the traced outline closely, and the string is straightened to measure its length. This measurement provides the exact circumference of the tree's cross-section for reference. Once the outline is traced, specific points along the outline are assigned coordinates in Euclidean space. These points are marked on the graph paper, and their coordinates (x, y) are recorded, ensuring they are spaced to accurately represent the shape of the cross-section.

In the calculation process, the assigned coordinates are used to calculate the distance between each pair of points using the Euclidean distance formula in two dimensions (Maxim et al., 2020) .The calculated circumference is then compared with the exact circumference measured earlier. The error is determined by subtracting the calculated circumference from the exact circumference. This error provides insight into the accuracy of the calculated perimeter compared to the actual measurement. Below are the distance and error formula used:

$$\text{Distance} = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}$$

$$\text{Error} = \text{Exact Circumference} - \text{Calculated Circumference.}$$

In the error convergence analysis process, the entire procedure is repeated five times, with the number of coordinates used to trace the tree cross-section increasing in each iteration. The behaviour of the errors can be observed in this process. After completing all iterations, the pattern of errors observed

in each trial is analysed. Errors are plotted against the number of coordinates used in each trial using Excel. An equation is then fitted to the data points to visualize how the error changes with the number of coordinates.

Lastly, in the algorithm development process, after confirming through analysis that the error converges to zero, the next step is to create a MATLAB algorithm based on the analysed formula. This application is designed to help users accurately calculate the perimeter of geometric shapes. The algorithm provides a user-friendly interface, allowing users to input relevant parameters, such as coordinates, and efficiently obtain the perimeter calculation.

2.2 Material

The subject used in this project is a cross-section of a cedar tree in Hitachi City. The algorithm used to develop the Trace-It application is implemented in MATLAB.

3. FINDINGS

After carefully tracing the outline of the tree cross-section with a piece of string and measuring its length, the string measured 23.15 cm.

Figure 1. Traced tree ring's

3.1 Distance Calculation of Coordinates in Euclidean Space

A total of 20 coordinates were spaced as accurately as possible to represent the shape of the tree ring's cross-section.

Table 1. Distances between 20 Coordinates.

No.	x	y	Distance
1	3.6	7.8	1.11803399
2	4	7.8	0.4
3	4.5	7.7	0.50990195
4	4.9	7.6	0.41231056
5	7.2	5.6	3.04795013
6	7.3	5.2	0.41231056
7	7.4	4.6	0.60827625
8	6.9	2.2	2.45153013
9	6.3	1.5	0.92195445
10	5.5	1	0.94339811
11	3.8	0.5	1.77200451
12	3.2	0.5	0.6

13	1.2	1.2	2.11896201
14	0.3	2.6	1.6643317
15	0.15	3.7	1.11018017
16	0.2	4.5	0.80156098
17	1.2	6.55	2.28089895
18	1.5	6.9	0.46097722
19	2	7.3	0.64031242
20	2.5	7.6	0.58309519
Perimeter			22.8579893

3.2 Error Comparison

The errors were determined by subtracting the calculated perimeter (22.8580) from the measured string length (23.15cm).

$$\text{Error} = 23.15 - 22.8580 = 0.292\text{cm.}$$

The coordinates were then increased by 5 for each of the 5 iterations to determine the error for each iteration.

Table 2. Distances between 25 Coordinates.

No.	x	y	Distance(cm)
1	3.6	7.8	0.6
2	4	7.8	0.4
3	4.5	7.7	0.50990195
4	4.9	7.6	0.41231056
5	6.8	6.3	2.30217289
6	7.2	5.6	0.80622577
7	7.3	5.2	0.41231056
8	7.4	4.6	0.60827625
9	6.9	2.2	2.45153013
10	6.7	1.9	0.36055513
11	6.3	1.5	0.56568542
12	5.5	1	0.94339811
13	3.8	0.5	1.77200451
14	3.2	0.5	0.6
15	1.6	0.9	1.64924225
16	1.2	1.2	0.5
17	0.3	2.6	1.6643317
18	0.15	3.7	1.11018017
19	0.2	4.5	0.80156098
20	0.3	5	0.50990195
21	1.2	6.55	1.79234483
22	1.5	6.9	0.46097722
23	2	7.3	0.64031242
24	2.5	7.6	0.58309519
25	3	7.8	0.53851648
PERIMETER			22.9948

Table 3. Distances between 30 Coordinates.

No.	x	y	Distance(cm)
1	3.6	7.8	0.6
2	4	7.8	0.4
3	4.5	7.7	0.50990195
4	4.9	7.6	0.41231056
5	5.4	7.4	0.53851648
6	6.8	6.3	1.78044938
7	7.2	5.6	0.80622577
8	7.3	5.2	0.41231056
9	7.4	4.6	0.60827625
10	7.3	3.1	1.50332964
11	6.9	2.2	0.98488578
12	6.7	1.9	0.36055513
13	6.3	1.5	0.56568542
14	5.5	1	0.94339811
15	5	0.7	0.58309519
16	3.8	0.5	1.21655251
17	3.2	0.5	0.6
18	1.6	0.9	1.64924225
19	1.2	1.2	0.5
20	0.9	1.5	0.42426407
21	0.3	2.6	1.25299641
22	0.15	3.7	1.11018017
23	0.2	4.5	0.80156098
24	0.3	5	0.50990195
25	0.5	5.5	0.53851648
26	1.2	6.55	1.26194295
27	1.5	6.9	0.46097722
28	2	7.3	0.64031242
29	2.5	7.6	0.58309519
30	3	7.8	0.53851648
PERIMETER			23.0970

Table 4. Distances between 35 Coordinates.

No.	x	y	Distance(cm)
1	3.6	7.8	0.6
2	4	7.8	0.4
3	4.5	7.7	0.50990195
4	4.9	7.6	0.41231056
5	5.4	7.4	0.53851648
6	6.3	6.7	1.14017543

7	6.8	6.3	0.64031242
8	7.2	5.6	0.80622577
9	7.3	5.2	0.41231056
10	7.4	4.6	0.60827625
11	7.3	3.1	1.50332964
12	7.1	2.7	0.4472136
13	6.9	2.2	0.53851648
14	6.7	1.9	0.36055513
15	6.3	1.5	0.56568542
16	5.5	1	0.94339811
17	5	0.7	0.58309519
18	4.5	0.6	0.50990195
19	3.8	0.5	0.70710678
20	3.2	0.5	0.6
21	1.6	0.9	1.64924225
22	1.2	1.2	0.5
23	0.9	1.5	0.42426407
24	0.5	2.1	0.72111026
25	0.3	2.6	0.53851648
26	0.15	3.7	1.11018017
27	0.2	4.5	0.80156098
28	0.3	5	0.50990195
29	0.5	5.5	0.53851648
30	0.8	5.9	0.5
31	1.2	6.55	0.76321688
32	1.5	6.9	0.46097722
33	2	7.3	0.64031242
34	2.5	7.6	0.58309519
35	3	7.8	0.53851648
PERIMETER			23.1062

Table 5. Distances between 40 Coordinates.

No.	x	y	Distance(cm)
1	3.6	7.8	0.6
2	4	7.8	0.4
3	4.5	7.7	0.509901951
4	4.9	7.6	0.412310563
5	5.4	7.4	0.538516481
6	5.8	7	0.565685425
7	6.3	6.7	0.583095189
8	6.8	6.3	0.640312424

9	7.2	5.6	0.806225775
10	7.3	5.2	0.412310563
11	7.4	4.6	0.608276253
12	7.4	4	0.6
13	7.3	3.1	0.905538514
14	7.1	2.7	0.447213595
15	6.9	2.2	0.538516481
16	6.7	1.9	0.360555128
17	6.3	1.5	0.565685425
18	5.8	1.2	0.583095189
19	5.5	1	0.360555128
20	5	0.7	0.583095189
21	4.5	0.6	0.509901951
22	3.8	0.5	0.707106781
23	3.2	0.5	0.6
24	2.5	0.6	0.707106781
25	1.6	0.9	0.948683298
26	1.2	1.2	0.5
27	0.9	1.5	0.424264069
28	0.5	2.1	0.721110255
29	0.3	2.6	0.538516481
30	0.2	3.1	0.509901951
31	0.15	3.7	0.602079729
32	0.2	4.5	0.801560977
33	0.3	5	0.509901951
34	0.5	5.5	0.538516481
35	0.8	5.9	0.5
36	1.2	6.55	0.763216876
37	1.5	6.9	0.460977223
38	2	7.3	0.640312424
39	2.5	7.6	0.583095189
40	3	7.8	0.538516481
PERIMETER			23.1257

The table below represents the error obtained from each iteration

Table 6. Error Comparison.

Iteration	No.data	Perimeter	Exact	Error
1	20	22.8580	23.15	0.292
2	25	22.9948	23.15	0.1552

3	30	23.097	23.15	0.0530
4	35	23.1062	23.15	0.0438
5	40	23.1257	23.15	0.0243

An equation was fitted to the data points to visualize how the error changed with the number of coordinates.

Figure 2. Error Curve.

3.2 Algorithm Development

The algorithm was developed using MATLAB App Designer. The app functions to assist users in determining the circumference of an object. In my project, the object of interest is the cross-section of a tree from Hitachi City. The app consists of three main panels, which are:

FIRST PANEL

Figure 3. First Panel: Welcome Panel.

There is only one button, labelled 'Start Button.' Users can press it to navigate to the second panel.

SECOND PANEL

Figure 4. Second Panel: Image Panel.

Table 7. Image Panel Button Explanations.

<p>Figure 5. Tutorial Button.</p>	<p>The 'Tutorial' button functions by allowing users to read the tutorial by simply hovering the cursor over it.</p>
<p>Figure 6. Reset Button.</p>	<p>The 'Reset' button functions by allowing users to clear all the data and graphs generated by the app.</p>

<p>Figure 7. Coordinates' Number Button.</p>	<p>The '25', '30', '35', and '40' buttons function by allowing users to input their own data based on the number they select.</p>
<p>Figure 8. Paste Button.</p>	<p>The 'Paste' button functions by allowing users to paste their own data instead of entering it manually. The data must be in a non-separated format.</p>
<p>Figure 9. Generate Button.</p>	<p>The 'Generate' button functions by creating a graph based on the data entered by the users.</p>
<p>Figure 10. Next Button</p>	<p>The 'Next' button functions by navigating users to the third panel.</p>

THIRD PANEL

Figure 11. Third Panel: Results Panel

Table 8. Results Panel Button Explanations.

<p>Figure 12. Distance Button</p>	<p>The 'Distance' button functions by adding a new column to the table and calculating the distance between each pair of points.</p>
<p>Figure 13. Circumference Button</p>	<p>The 'Circumference' button functions by summing up all the distances to calculate the object's circumference.</p>

4. DISCUSSION

The aim of this project is to obtain an accurate algorithm in MATLAB to compute the perimeter of a cedar tree cross-section. The findings presented here indicated that the use of additional coordinates in outlining the tree's shape enhanced the calculated perimeter values. When more points were added, the error reduced and converge to zero, making the algorithm accurate.

This particular algorithm can be deemed efficient and easy to use when it comes to calculating perimeters of shapes of different complexity. Its user-friendly methodology leads to a significant reduction in time, energy, and resources. The algorithm's accuracy is guaranteed, as it has been tested by extensive convergence analysis.

Thus, the proposed algorithm known as Trace-It can be viewed as a handy approach to perimeter calculation with a certain potential for its further development to embrace more extensive uses.

5. CONCLUSION

In this research, an algorithm called Trace-It are developed in MATLAB for calculating the circumference of geometric shapes which is a cross-section of cedar tree in this case. The algorithm is useful in reducing the chances of errors as more coordinates were being defined, and nearly precise perimeter was obtained. The tool is particularly useful to compute the perimeter in various field such as architecture, forestry and fashion industry. Further development can be conducted to accommodate three dimensional geometry while Utilizing this current research. In general, Trace-It algorithm demonstrates efficacy and feasibility in calculating perimeter of various object.

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